

Société Française pour l'Etude des Toxines

Association N° 1438, JO du 20 Juillet 1994

N° SIREN : 451 976 567

N° SIRET : 451 976 567 00011

CERTIFICATE

During the RT29 organized by the SFET on 30 November and 01 December 2023, Dr **Juan Carlos Galindo** presented a conference entitled "Building up a pipeline for assessing potential molecular targets of conotoxins with unknown mode of action". Mr **Antonio Caballero Foncubierta** presented a poster entitled "Proteomics reveals a compartmentalized venom duct in the two phylogenetically related cone snails *Rhombiconus fuscatus* (Born, 1778) and *R. imperialis* (Linnaeus, 1758)". Both of them co-authored the two presentations during this meeting.

The 2 summaries of the authors' oral communication and poster will be included in an invitation article entitled: "Report from the 29th Meeting on Toxinology, "Toxins: From the Wild to the Lab", organized by the French Society of Toxinology on 30 November and 01 December 2023" which will be submitted to the journal *Toxins* by the end of January 2024.

Valbonne, 18 of January 2024

Dr. Sylvie DIOCHOT

On behalf of the SFET Organizing Committee

<http://www.sfet.asso.fr/>

Présidente : Dr. Sylvie DIOCHOT : CNRS IPMC 660 Route des Lucioles 06560 Valbonne -France (diochot@ipmc.cnrs.fr)